

Eroziyalangan tog‘ tuproqlarida gumusning to‘planishida tuproqning mexanik tarkibi, ona jinslar tarkibi va joyning reliefi, ekspozitsiyasi kabi omillar muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ya‘ni yengil mexanik tarkibli tuproqlarda gumus va o‘simliklar uchun zarur oziq moddalar kam va singdirish qobiliyati past bo‘lganidan, eroziya jarayonlarini rivojlanishi ancha jadal kechadi.

Shuningdek, yengil mexanik tarkibli tuproqlarda aeratsiya va issiqlik yaxshi bo‘lganidan organik qoldiqlar tez minerallashib parchalanib ketishi izchil kechishi natijasida gumus kam to‘planadi. Mexanik tarkibi og‘ir tuproqlarda, aksincha, gumus ko‘p to‘planadi. Og‘ir mexanik tarkibli tuproqlarda gumus moddasini ko‘p saqlashi hamda mayda zarrachalarning ko‘pligi, qolaversa karbonatlarning ishtirok etishi natijasida bu tuproqlarda suvga chidamli agregatlar shakllanadi. Shuningdek, o‘simlik qoplaminig turli-tumanligi, tuproq yuzasini batamom bekitishi ham tabiiy sharoitda agregatlarni hosil bo‘lishiga qo‘shimcha sharoit yaratadi. Natijada bunday sharoitda gumusga boy, unumdorlik xususiyatlari yuqori bo‘lgan va eroziya jarayonlariga bardoshli tuproqlar shakllanadi.

Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, tadqiq etilgan lalmi tuproqlarining mexanik tarkibiga ko‘ra, qiyalikni har-xil ekspozitsiyalarida eroziya ta‘sirida tuproq tarkibida keskin o‘zgarishlar kechadi: mexanik tarkib yengillashishi, il va mayda chang fraksiyalarni kamayishi, yirik fraksiyalarning ko‘payishi kabi jarayonlar kuzatildi. Bo‘z tuproqlarga nisbatan tog‘ jigarrang tuproqlarida fizik loy miqdori oshib borishi, janubiy qiyalik tuproqlarida mexanik tarkibning yengillashishi kuzatiladi. Bu jarayon bir tomondan tuproq paydo qiluvchi ona jinsga bog‘liq bo‘lsa, ikkinchi tomondan eroziya jarayoniga bog‘liqdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

1. Курвантаев Р., Кузибоев О. и др. «Влияние орошения на агрофизические свойства такырно-луговые почв Каршинской степи» Материалы V съезда общества почвоведов и агрохимиков Узбекистана. Ташкент 2010 г, с 106-109.
2. Ташкузиев М.М. – Химический и минералогический состав фракций механических элементов целинного и орошаемого типичного серозема. Автореф. канд. дисс., Ташкент, 1973, - 10-25 с.
3. Хоназаров А., Турсунов Л., Фахрутдинова М., Комилова Д., Ўзбекистон тоғ тупроқлари Тошкент 2009, 231- б.
4. Шадиева Н.И. Абдурасулов Х.Х. Эргашев Б.Т. Вертикал зоналикда тарқалган лалми тупроқларнинг айрим физик хоссаларига эрозия жараёнларини таъсири, /Ўзбекистонда ғаллачиликнинг яратилган илмий асослари ва уни ривожлантириш истиқболлари, халқаро илмий-амалий анжумани материаллари. Жиззах. Ғаллаорол 2012 й. 300-302 б.
5. Шадиева Н.И. Эрозияланган тоғ тупроқларининг механик таркиби, уни тупроқ унумдорлиги ва гумус тўпланишидаги ахамияти // Вестник аграрной науки Узбекистана. – 2016. – № 3. – Б. 34-37.

SOIL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE POLAR URALS DEVELOPED ON CARBONATE ROCKS

Shamrikova E., Zhangurov E., Korolev M.

*Soil Science Department, Institute of Biology, Komi Federal Research Centre, Ural Branch of RAS,
Syktyvkar, 167982, Russian Federation,
e-mail: shamrikovaelena@yandex.ru*

Annotation. *The article deals with the peculiarities of soil formation in mountain-tundra landscapes of the northern part of the Bolshoi Paipudynsky Ridge (Polar Urals). It is shown that humification processes take place in conditions of high carbonate content, alkaline reaction of the medium, migration of organic matter deep into the profile due to leaching water regime.*

Keywords: *Polar Urals, carbonates, cryogenesis, pyrogenesis*

Introduction. The Polar Urals is the northern end of the Ural mountain belt and is a mountainous folded area (65°40'–68°30' N). Despite a long history of research, the soils and vegetation of this region have not been sufficiently studied, especially in the most inaccessible areas. Significant size of the region (about

25000 km²), peculiarities of geomorphology, complex palaeogeographic conditions of sedimentation (cover and mountain-valley glaciations) cause significant biodiversity of terrestrial ecosystems. The wide distribution of different soil-forming rocks determines a significant diversity of different soil types and subtypes. Given the complex climatic fluctuations of the late Holocene and the dynamics of vegetation at the upper limit of tree species distribution, this region is an interesting and promising area for soil-geographic research.

One of the poorly studied aspects for soils of mountain-tundra landscapes is the identification of the role of pyrogenesis – an important ecological factor in the functioning of the ecosystem as a whole and its individual components. To date, soils with evidence of pyrogenesis in lowland landscapes have been much better studied [1; 5; 9] than soils in mountain ecosystems [4]. Such information is not available for the Polar Urals region we studied.

The aim of this work is to identify morphogenetic features and to assess the distribution of different forms of carbon and nitrogen in the soils of the Polar Urals.

Materials and Methods. The study area is located in the northern part of the Big Paipudynsky Ridge (67°13'N and 65°28'E), 70 km north of the Arctic Circle. Soils on the geomorphological altitude profile: from the top to the bottom of the slope were selected as objects of study. The soils are formed on the eluvial-deluvial thickness of marbled limestone and redeposited loamy-light (medium) loamy sediments in the conditions of karst sinkholes. Genetic horizons and soils were diagnosed according to [3]. Analytical data were obtained in the Ecoanalit laboratory and in the Soil Science Department of the Institute of Biology of the Komi Scientific Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Descriptions of all soils were accompanied by colour determination according to the Mansell scale. Samples of carbonaceous particles were examined using a digital microscope (20 to 300x) with a 5 Mpx camera, and their shape, size and structure were determined.

Results and Discussion. The morphological structure of the soils is considered on the example of 3 section.

Section 6. Altitude 264 m, top of the uval. The vegetation cover is *Dryas tundra* (*Dryas octopetala*). Profile structure: O (0–1 cm) – Ah1 (1–10 cm) – Ah2 (10–25 cm) – Ah@ (25–35 cm) – Bca (35–45 cm) – Cca (45–55 cm). Soil: Leptic Skeletic Calcaric Regosol.

Section 5 located on a concave U-shaped slope on redeposited loose sediments sharply underlain by massive slabs. The absolute height is 246 m. The vegetation cover is a grass-willow community. Profile structure: O (0–2 cm) – H1 (2–5 cm) – H2 (5–15/20 cm) – Bwca1 (15/20–30 cm) – [coals 20–30 cm] – Bwca2 (30–45 cm). Soil: Mollic Leptic Calcaric Stagnosol Skeletic soil.

Section 7k. A conical sinkhole with a diameter of up to 5 m in the upper part of the sinkhole, the section was laid at the bottom of the sinkhole. Absolute height 230 m. Ground cover includes green moss and lichen. Profile structure: Oao (0–2 cm) – Ah (2–10 cm) – Bhs (10–25 cm) – Bs (25–35 cm) – Bw1 (35–50 cm) – [coals] 35–50 cm – Bw2 (50–80 cm). Soil: Stagnic Entic Podzol Skeletic.

The morphological descriptions of the soil sections revealed a complex system of horizons and subhorizons, which largely determines the diversity of soil types and subtypes and the spatial variability of the upper and middle horizons, even at small distances. The soils studied are characterised by a clear differentiation into genetic horizons [7]. Below the low moisture litter-peat horizon O, dark humus horizons Ah are formed, which are diagnosed by the presence of dark (from dark brown to black) colour (10YR 3/3 – 3/1; 10YR 2/1) and unstable lumpy structure with sharp transition in colour to the underlying horizons. In the Ah horizon there is a minor admixture of plant remains of varying degrees of decomposition and post-fire charcoal inclusions. As a result of the high friability, the presence of carbonate rocks and the lack of filtration capacity, there is no frost in the soils. The maximum limestone content is characteristic of section 6 (70–80 % of the horizon volume), while in the other sections it occurs only from a depth of 45–50 cm [6, 7]. Sections 7k and 5, formed under accumulative and transit-accumulative conditions, are characterised by the presence of a specific structural organisation, strongly expressed in the morphology.

At the top of the uval (section 6), the cryogenic microrelief is clearly expressed: the areas without vegetation cover have a specific 4–5–6 coal geometric shape and account for 60–70% of the total area (Fig. 1). Despite the absence of underlying permafrost in the soil profile, the presence of cryogenic microrelief indicates intense cryogenic phenomena.

6. Leptic Skeletic Calcaric Regosol

5. Mollic Leptic Calcaric Stagnosol Skeletic soil

7k. Stagnic Entic Podzol Skeletic

Fig. 1. Soil profiles and vegetation.

The presence of highly weathered fine gravel and rock fragments (3–10 mm) in the soil profile of the Leptic Skeletal Calcareous Regosol, which are easily destroyed by pressure, indicates intensive processes of their physical and chemical disintegration (Fig. 2). At the same time, the profile distribution of skeletal-coarse clastic fractions (1–2 mm, 2–5 mm, 5–10 mm and > 10 mm) and fine-grained soils (<1 mm) has a specific distribution, which is uncharacteristic for soils of mountain tundras on dense rocks.

The upper and middle horizons are characterised by the maximum content of skeletal fractions (> 1 mm), the proportion of which decreases sharply with depth. The content of fine soil grains (<1 mm) shows an inverse dependence. The main mechanism revealing the specificity of the profile distribution and the 'fine soil/skeleton' ratio is related to intensive processes of cryogenic weathering in the mineral part of the soil at depth (32–60 cm). The 'reduced intensity' of cryogenesis in the upper dark-coloured and organic matter-impregnated horizons (0–32 cm) is determined by good aggregation and the presence of 'protective films' of organic matter over the entire surface of the mineral grains of the fine soil grains.

Cryometamorphic horizons are yellowish-brown in colour (10YR 5/4; 10YR 4/3); horizontal divisibility of the soil mass is observed: fragile lenticular aggregates 5–8 mm thick are scattered in finely lumpy (in some places angular-crumbly) individuals with dimensions of 4–7 mm horizontally and 3–4 mm vertically [7]. The melkozem of the cryometamorphic horizon actively boils under the influence of 10% HCl. The formation of such a structure occurs under the influence of repeated freeze-thaw cycles in certain moisture and temperature ranges, which has been demonstrated for many types of soils, both in plain and mountainous landscapes [9; 10].

A common morphological feature of the sections compared is the presence of intensely dark-colored pyrogenic horizons, localized both in the upper part of the soil (6; 5) and in the form of buried horizons in the middle and lower parts (5 and 7k). This is probably related to erosional processes of overdeposition (planar washing away of the upper soil layers during active snowmelt and high rainfall in summer). In the course of microscopic examination of the post-fire charcoal particles, their basic morphometric data were characterized. We found that charcoal fragments differ from the dark mineral particles of the humus horizons in their black color (2.5Y N2/ black; 10YR 2/1 black), reflectivity, strength, shape and size.

Depending on the shape (ratio of long axis to short axis), the following types are conventionally distinguished: 'cubic', 'elongated', 'sharp-angled' and 'angular-cut'. When touched with tweezers, charcoal is

relatively easy to break into small angular fragments, which often show wood structure. The character of charcoal distribution in soil profiles is largely determined by local factors (character of microrelief and content of crushed limestone) and the possibility of its further vertical and horizontal migration.

Fig. 2. Distribution of fine-grained (<1 mm) and skeletal (>1 mm) particles in the Leptic Skeletal Calcareous Regosol profile (dry sieving).

No charcoal particles were found in organogenic horizons O. In section 6 (top of the uval) in Ah horizons, the distribution of charcoal particles has the following regularities.

Table

Soil characteristics

Horizon	pH _{H2O}	C _{inorg}	C _{org}	N _{tot}	N-NH ₄ ⁺	N-NO ₃ ⁻	C/N
		%			mg/kg		
6. Leptic Skeletic Calcaric Regosol							
O	7.57	7.03	16.6	0.87	49.45	10.90	22
Ah1	8.04	8.11	3.5	0.32	14.18		13
Ah2	8.08	5.02	7.4	0.54	13.60		16
Ah@	7.98	4.40	7.7	0.62	12.45	0.00	14
Bca	8.32	10.32	1.4		1.08		-
Cca	8.50	12.24	0.0	0.0	0.91		-
5. Mollic Leptic Calcaric Stagnosol Skeletic soil							
O	6.90		30.2	1.96	135.98	10.28	18
H1	6.59		11.0	0.98	35.80		13
H2	6.97	0.0	7.6	0.69	15.88		13
Bwca1	7.40		1.8	0.15	4.82	0.00	14
Bwca2	7.73	0.66	0.9	0.13	3.30		8
7k. Stagnic Entic Podzol Skeletic							
Oao	4.91		18.0	0.97	64.05	36.83	22
Ah	5.07		6.5	0.34	19.21		22
Bhs	5.11		7.7	0.36	15.84		25
Bs	5.33	0.0	1.4	0.103	8.50	0.00	16
Bw1	5.32		0.97	0.076	9.94		15
Bw2	4.91		0.98	0.078	9.94		15

The upper horizons (1–10 cm and 10–25 cm) contain a significant amount of fine coals of 1 mm or less, probably related to the age of the fire event and subsequent erosive surface flow down the slope. In addition, cryogenic microrelief is pronounced in this area; active cryoturbation processes, including physical disintegration processes, largely determine the distribution of coal material. In the lower horizon, at a depth of 25–35 cm, the content of large coal particles increases significantly (from 3–5 mm to 10–12 mm), which, according to a number of authors [5; 8], indicates a local type of fire. The presence of a thick buried layer of coals (with sizes up to 5–6 mm and more) at a depth of 35–50 cm in the karst sinkholes (located downslope from sections 6 and 5) demonstrates the profile of the buried soil with a clear differentiation into genetic horizons formed as a result of erosion processes – post-fire deposits.

The soils are considered to be characterized by a neutral to slightly alkaline reaction of the medium throughout the profile (Table). Humification processes take place under conditions of high carbonate content, alkaline reaction of the medium due to the dominance of $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$ in the soil solution, migration of organic matter deep into the profile due to the leaching water regime. These factors, together with the dominance of calciphilic vegetation, taking into account the pyrogenic influence, preservation, decomposition and biological activity of the microflora, leading to the dark coloring of the upper part of the soil profile of the soils studied [7]. The carbon content of inorganic compounds increases with depth, its only source being the carbonate parent rock. Inorganic nitrogen (sum of $\text{N}-\text{NO}_3^-$ и $\text{N}-\text{NH}_4^+$) of soils is less than 1 % of its total content in soils.

Summary and Suggestions. Thus, the specificity of factors and conditions of soil formation (mosaic vegetation cover, hydrothermal regime, different thickness of fine-grained loam and debris layers, etc.) determine different manifestations and combinations of elementary soil-forming processes: surface accumulation of coarse humus litter; intensive humus accumulation and humus leaching; cryogenic metamorphism of mineral masses (cryogenic restructuring); disintegration of crushed stone/dust to fine-grained stage; leaching of calcareous rock. Pyrogenesis, as an important factor of modern soil formation, activates the manifestation of exogenous geomorphological processes and leads to the formation of soils with a polycyclic profile.

Funding. This research was funded by the RSF, grant № 24-27-00231.

Reference

1. Bobrovsky M.V., Kupriaynov D.A., Khanina L.G. Anthracological and morphological analysis of soils for the reconstruction of the forest ecosystem history (Meshchera Lowlands, Russia). *Quaternary International*. N 516, 2019. P. 70-82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2018.06.033>
2. Goryachkin S.V., Shavrina E.V. Evolution and dynamics of soil-geomorphic systems in karst landscapes of the European North // *Eurasian Soil Science*. 1997. V. 30. № 10. P 1045-1055.
3. IUSS Working Group WRB, World Reference Base for Soil Resources 2014, Update 2015, International Soil Classification System for Naming Soils and Creating Legends for Soil Maps, World Soil Resources Reports No. 106 (Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome, 2015; Moscow State Univ., Moscow, 2017).
4. Maslov M.N., Maslova O.A., Kopeina E.I. Changes in the Pools of Total and Labile Soil Organic Carbon during Post-Fire Succession in the Khibiny Mountain Tundra Ecosystems. *Eurasian Soil Science*. 2020. V. 53. N 3. P. 330-338. DOI: [10.1134/S1064229320030047](https://doi.org/10.1134/S1064229320030047)
5. Mergelov N., Petrov D., Zazovskaya E., Dolgikh A., Golyeva A., Matskovsky V., Bichurin R., Turchinskaya S., Belyaev V., Goryachkin S. Soils in karst sinkholes record the holocene history of local forest fires at the North of European Russia // *Forests*. 2020. V. 11. N 12. P. 1268. DOI: [10.3390/f11121268](https://doi.org/10.3390/f11121268)
6. Shamrikova, Zhangurov E.V., Kubik O.S., Korolev M.A. Composition of water extracts of plants, soils on calcareous rocks, and surface water in the northern part of the Polar Urals // *Eurasian Soil Science*. 2021. V. 54. N 8. P. 1161-1175. DOI: [10.1134/S1064229321080159](https://doi.org/10.1134/S1064229321080159)
7. Shamrikova E.V., Zhangurov E.V., Kulyugina E.E., Korolev M.A., Kubik O.S., Tumanova E.A. Soils and soil cover of mountainous tundra landscapes of the Polar Urals on calcareous rocks: diversity, taxonomy, nitrogen and carbon patterns. *Eurasian Soil Science*. 2020. V. 53. N 9. P. 1206-1221. DOI: [10.1134/S106422932009015X](https://doi.org/10.1134/S106422932009015X)
8. Tinner, W.; Hofstetter, S.; Zeugin, F.; Conedera, M.; Wohlgemuth, T.; Zimmermann, L.; Zweifel, R. Long-distance transport of macroscopic charcoal by an intensive crown fire in the Swiss Alps-implications for fire history reconstruction. *Holocene* 2006. N 16 287-292. <https://doi.org/10.1191/0959683606hl925rr>
9. Zhangurov E.V., Lebedeva M.P., Zaboeva I.V. Microstructure of genetic horizons in automorphic soils of the Timan Ridge. *Eurasian Soil Science*. 2011. V. 44. N 3. P. 288-299. DOI: [10.1134/S1064229311030203](https://doi.org/10.1134/S1064229311030203)
10. Zhangurov E.V., Startsev V.V., Dubrovskiy Ya.A., Degteva S.V., Dumov A.A. Morphogenetic Features of

UO‘T: 631.674:631.811.98:633.51

SUG‘ORISH TARTIBI, KO‘CHAT QALINLIGI VA OZIQLANTIRISH ME‘YORLARIGA BOG‘LIQ HOLDA BIOSTIMULYATOR QO‘LLASHNING G‘O‘ZANI QURUQ MASSA TO‘PLASHIGA TA‘SIRI

Shamsiyev A.S., Muxammadiyeva O.N.

Toshkent davlat agrar universiteti

Ziyatov Musulman Panjiyevich

PSUYAITI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o‘rta tolali S-8298 g‘o‘za navini Toshkent viloyatining tipik bo‘z tuproqlari sharoitida turli sug‘orish (tomchilatib, egatlab) usullarida quruq massa to‘plashi, ko‘chat qalinligi, oziqlantirish me‘yorlari hamda biostimulyatorlarning ta‘sirini o‘rganish bo‘yicha olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijalari tahlillari keltirilgan. Tadqiqotlar natijasida g‘o‘zani quruq massa to‘plashining yuqori ko‘rsatkichlari tomchilatib sug‘orishda tuproq namligi ChDNS ga nisbatan 70-70-60 % sug‘orish tartibida 100-110 ming/ga ko‘chat qalinligida, mineral o‘g‘itlar N-200, P-140, K-100 kg/ga me‘yorda qo‘llanilganda olingan yoki egatlab sug‘orishga mutanosib ravishda bir o‘simlikda 1,3; 1,5; 1,3; 4,4 va 8,5 g. ga yuqori bo‘lgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tomchilatib va egatlab sug‘orish, mineral o‘g‘itlar me‘yori, ko‘chat qalinligi, biostimulyatorlar, paxta hosili.

Аннотация. В Статье приведены результаты научных исследований по изучению влияния различных способов (капельного, бороздкового) полива на густоту стояния, норм минерального питания, а также биостимуляторов на накопление сухой массы хлопчатника средневолокнистого сорта С-8298 проведенных в условиях типичных серозёмов Ташкентской области. В результате исследований наибольшие показатели накопления сухой массы хлопчатником в среднем на одно растение были получены при капельном орошении, режиме предполивного увлажнения почвы 70-70-60 % от НПВ, густоте стояния 100-110 тыс/га, применении минеральных удобрений нормами N-200, P-140, K-100 кг/га, что по сравнению с бороздковым способом полива было выше на 1,3; 1,5; 1,3; 4,4 и 8,5 г. соответственно.

Ключевые слова: Хлопчатник, рост и развитие, густота стояния, капельный полив, биостимуляторы, минеральные удобрения.

Annotation. The article presents an analysis of scientific research results on the accumulation of dry mass, plant density, nutrient application rates, and the effects of biostimulants on the medium-fiber cotton variety S-8298 under different irrigation methods (drip and furrow) in the typical gray soils of the Tashkent region. The study examines the impact of biostimulant application in relation to different nutrient application rates. The results indicate that the highest dry mass accumulation in cotton was observed under drip irrigation with a soil moisture regime maintained at 70-70-60% of the field capacity, a plant density of 100,000–110,000 plants per hectare, and the application of mineral fertilizers at rates of N-200, P-140, and K-100 kg/ha. Compared to furrow irrigation, this resulted in higher dry mass accumulation per plant by 1.3 g, 1.5 g, 1.3 g, 4.4 g, and 8.5 g, respectively.

Key words: Cotton, growth, and development, seedling, thickness, drip irrigation, biostimulants, mineral fertilizers.

Kirish. So‘nggi yillarda jahon paxtachiligida g‘o‘zani sug‘orish va oziqlantirishda yangi innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo‘llash orqali tuproqda o‘simlik ildizi tarqalgan faol qatlamni bir tekis namlash hamda mineral o‘g‘itlardan foydalanish koeffitsiyentini oshirishga erishilmoqda.

Respublikaning sug‘oriladigan maydonlarida g‘o‘za va unga izdosh qishloq xo‘jaligi ekinlarini suvga bo‘lgan talabini o‘rganish, sug‘orish usuli va texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish, maqbul rejimlarini aniqlash masalalari ustida, turli tuproqlar sharoitlarida izlanishlar o‘tkazilgan.